

Deliverable 4.7: Upgrading multidisciplinary clinical expertise

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Contents

Basic information.....	3
Executive summary	4
1 Description of work & main achievements	4
1.1 Regular meetings with clinicians – BMC SAV.....	4
1.2 Digital education – e-lectures	6
1.3 Invited lectures	9
1.4 Future planning	10
2 Deviation from the workplan	12
3 Conclusion	12

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Basic information

Project title	Strategies to strengthen scientific excellence and innovation capacity for early diagnosis of gastrointestinal cancers
Project acronym	VISION
Call	H2020-WIDESPREAD-2018-2020
Topic	WIDESPREAD-03-2018
Project type	Coordination and Supporting Action (CSA)
Grant Agreement No.	857381
Nature	R (Document, report - excluding the periodic and final reports);
Dissemination level	PU (Public, fully open, e.g. web);

Executive summary

Work package 4 is dedicated to mining and bridging the gaps between research and clinics. As cancer patients' treatment is becoming more and more complex the concept of a multidisciplinary team working for patient's benefit is considered the gold standard for improving cancer care. Within cancer multidisciplinary team surgeons, oncologists, radiologists, pathologists, specialist cancer nurses, physicians, specialists in basic scientists and psychologists work the best way to treat cancer patients. A successful multidisciplinary health team leads to a comprehensive assessment of a patient's situation and works out a safer approach to treat each patient. Therefore, within the VISION project, it was foreseen that medical doctors during their specialization but also scientists will participate in such multidisciplinary teams within the hospital health care units participating in the project.

1 Description of work & main achievements

Tentative plans were made for medical doctors and scientists to visit the 2nd surgical clinic of NKUA participating in the project. Several activities including

- participating in ward rounds,
- attending presentation and review of high input clinical papers on surgical, medical oncology and pathology weekly,
- joining seminars on oncology topics by the experts on the field and
- actively engaged in multidisciplinary meetings where surgeons, medical oncologists, pathologists and scientists would discuss and plan the best available treatment of patients with GT cancer

were planned for upgrading multidisciplinary clinical expertise.

Dr Peter Dubovan, the medical doctor doing his specialization in Surgery, was the first to express interest to visit the 2nd Department of Surgery in Aretaieio Hospital and join the surgical team of Prof M. Konstadoulakis for a month in summer 2020. Unfortunately, due to the Covid-19 pandemic, his visit was postponed. Still, the invitation is valid and it will be hopefully realized when travelling will be allowed and the surgical clinic will return to its running routine.

1.1 Regular meetings with clinicians – BMC SAV

Before the initiation of the coronavirus pandemic, regular meetings of scientists from BMC SAV with Slovak clinicians were established to strengthen existing and create new functioning collaborations having a common goal - to be beneficial for patients. BMC SAV participated in the following joint meetings:

22nd meeting NOU-SAV-LFUK – October 23, 2019

Sampling and flow - studies of pancreatic Ca, breast Ca, CRC, TGCTs, haematological malignancies - recruitment update from 9/19 to 10/19 – K. Kaľavská, MD

Educational lectures:

- 1) Michal Mego, MD., DSc: Chemotherapy of advanced testicular tumours
- 2) Ján Tkáč, DSc: Glycosylation in the diagnosis of oncological diseases
- 3) Iveta Oravcová, MD. PhD – Department of Oncohematology LFUK and NOU - presentation of the project of biobanking of acute leukaemias in NOU - proposal for cooperation for workplaces BMC SAV, LFUK
- 4) Dr Palacka / Dr Slopovský – discussion on the possibility of epigenetic analyses of bladder Ca

23rd meeting NOU-SAV-LFUK – November 19, 2019

Sampling and flow - studies of pancreatic Ca, breast Ca, CRC, TGCTs, haematological malignancies - recruitment update for the last month – K. Kaľavská, MD

Educational lectures:

- 1) Michal Mego, MD, DSc: Adjuvant treatment of breast cancer (stage I-III)
- 2) Svetlana Školeková, PhD: Basic methods of culture and characterization of tumour cell lines
- 3) Conference reports - CA IX – Katarina Kaľavská, MD, Silvia Schmidtová, PhD
- 4) Progress of projects

25th meeting NOU-SAV-LFUK – January 22, 2020

Sampling and flow - studies of pancreatic Ca, breast Ca, CRC, TGCTs, haematological malignancies - recruitment update for the last month – K. Kaľavská, MD

Educational lectures:

- 1) Eva Zomborská, MD: Adjuvant treatment of colorectal cancer
- 2) Pavol Janega, MD: Tissue microarray, advantages and disadvantages
- 3) Progress of projects

26th meeting NOU-SAV-LFUK – February 26, 2020

Sampling and flow - studies of pancreatic Ca, breast Ca, CRC, TGCTs, haematological malignancies - recruitment update for the last month – K. Kaľavská, MD

Educational lectures:

- 1) Štefan Porsok, MD: Systemic treatment of colorectal cancer
- 2) Katarína Kaľavská, MD: Susceptibility gene screening methods (Crisp, siRNA, other)
- 3) Progress of projects

27th meeting NOU-SAV-LFUK – June 17, 2020

Sampling and flow - studies of pancreatic Ca, breast Ca, CRC, TGCTs, haematological malignancies - recruitment update for the last month - Dr Kaľavská

Educational lectures:

- 1) Michal Chovanec, MD, PhD: Adjuvant treatment of testicular tumours

2) Progress of projects

Regular meetings will continue as the pandemic situation improves.

1.2 Digital education – e-lectures

Nevertheless, even following the COVID-19 crisis and as all travel actions were suspended project partners agreed to follow a digital education action plan and to split any actions into theoretical and practical parts. Within this frame e-lectures, standard operating procedures derived as parts of training activities, and invited lectures of VISION, from which educational material can be found under the heading Educational Activities (https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1PZCR6QnBGzy3Olw3c_OOq1Vcu_hX9KXx?usp=sharing), are tending to assist those interested in participating in a multidisciplinary team for GI cancer patients to broaden their horizons in different aspects of scientific and medical issues and be able to offer high-quality care in GI patients.

Clinical Research Patients Enrollment

This Power Point presentation was prepared by

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National and Kapodistrian University of Athens

Within the VISION project for teaching purposes

Highest appreciation to all colleagues for their fruitful comments.

The role of surgery in the management of intermediate stage BCLC-B hepatocellular carcinoma

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Athens Medical School, NKUA
within the VISION project for teaching purposes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 857381

Pancreaticoduodenectomy in pancreatic cancer (Whipple procedure - state of the art)

This Power Point presentation was prepared by
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Within the VISION project for teaching purposes

Highest appreciation to all colleagues for their fruitful comments.

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Right colectomy: new concepts on classic surgery

P. Antonakis MD, PhD
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within the VISION project for teaching purposes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 857381

Robotic gastrectomy

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 857381

Principles of Cancer Genetic Counseling

This Power Point presentation was prepared by
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Within the VISION project for teaching purposes

Highest appreciation to all colleagues for their fruitful comments.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 857381

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The role of Genetic Predisposition in the diagnosis, treatment and prognosis of gastrointestinal cancer

This Power Point presentation was prepared by
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within the VISION project for teaching purposes.

Highest appreciation to all colleagues for their fruitful comments.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 857381

1.3 Invited lectures

Also, the three invited lectures performed by

- Prof. Alfredo Carrato entitled Challenges in exocrine pancreatic adenocarcinoma management on October 14, 2020
- Dr Julie Earl entitled Advances in familial pancreatic cancers on October 21, 2020, and
- Dr Laura Garcia Bermejo Molecular and Cellular mechanisms/biomarkers in PDAC presented on October 28, 2020

are estimated to assist the upgrading of multidisciplinary clinical expertise.

HORIZON 2020

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 857381

VISION

Challenges in exocrine pancreatic adenocarcinoma management

Strategies to strengthen scientific excellence and innovation capacity for early diagnosis of gastrointestinal cancers: GA 857381

Alfredo Carrato MD, PhD
Ramón y Cajal University Hospital, IRYCIS, CIBERONC
Alcalá University, Madrid

1.4 Future planning

The following activities are planned for the year 2021 as e-meetings due to the uncertainty of the pandemic's evolution.

The treatment landscape for hepatocellular carcinoma

Time	Subject
5 min	Welcome. Introduction and objectives Prof. Konstadoulakis M.
30 min (20' + 10')	Histological and molecular subtypes of hepatocellular carcinoma Prof. Tiniakou K.
30 min (20' + 10')	Locoregional therapies and patient profiling Prof. Elefsiniotis I.
30 min (20' + 10')	Surgical Treatment in HCC Prof. Dervenis Ch.
30' (20' + 10')	Systemic treatments and Immunotherapy in HCC Prof. Koskinas
5 min	Closing Remarks Prof. Konstadoulakis M.

Overview and future perspectives in colorectal cancer

Time	Subject
5 min	Welcome. Introduction, objectives of the meeting Prof. Konstadoulakis M.
20 min (15' + 5')	Hereditary colorectal cancer syndromes Dr. Kataki A.
20 min (15' + 5')	Histological and molecular subtypes in colorectal cancer Dr. Koniaris E.
20 min (15' + 5')	Surgery for Colon Cancer Prof. Dervenis Ch.
20 min (15' + 5')	Systemic therapies in Colorectal Cancer Prof. Papadimitriou
5 min	Closing Remarks Prof. Konstadoulakis M.

Diagnostic and therapeutic aspects of handling GP neuroendocrine tumours (GPNETs)

Time	Subject
5 min	Welcome. Introduction, objectives of the meeting. Prof. Konstadoulakis M.
30 min (20' + 10')	Introduction to GPNETs Prof. Mastorakos G.
30 min (20' + 10')	Surgery as a Treatment for GPNETs Prof. Dervenis Ch.
30 min (20' + 10')	Therapeutic Spectrum in GPNETs Dr. Alexandraki K.
5 min	Closing Remarks Prof. Konstadoulakis M.

2 Deviation from the workplan

Due to the current coronavirus pandemic situation, the intended visit could not be realized within the planned time frame. As soon as the restrictions due to COVID19 crisis are withdrawn medical students or residents would be able to join the everyday routine of a surgical clinic. Still, the theoretical expertise of those interested in the field is continuously enriched to enable them to get ready for the real clinical setting in near future.

3 Conclusion

Based on the belief that the current COVID crisis will change in 2021, we hope that it will be possible to implement the initially planned actions within the remaining time. Until then all consortium members will continue their efforts to further upgrade the multidisciplinary clinical expertise before it could be transferred into a real-life setting.